

IMPROVEMENT OF CAST IRON SURFACE BY USING ALLOY POWDERS ON THE MOLD

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SUMMARY: For coating functional layer on cast iron, mixed powders which consist of high performance powder and Ni-based alloy powder having low melting point are coated on the mold. By the heat of pouring, these powder layers are densified by a liquid-phase sintering and then jointed with cast iron. The coated cast iron obtained by mixed Fe-Cr alloy and self-fused Ni based alloy has substantial hardness (800•1000HV1) and good resistance to wet abrasion, and also by mixed Ni and Ni-P alloy has soft layer (100•200HV1) coating 10•20%Ni and therefore good corrosion resistance to spraying of 5%NaCl solution.

KEYWORDS: liquid-phase sintering, surface treatment, cast iron, abrasion resistance, corrosion resistance, alloy powder, mold, self-fused

INTRODUCTION

This investigation is one of the surface treatments or the coating methods of functional layer on cast iron. Mixed powders contained low melting point powder previously coated on the mold, is consolidated as a layer during liquid-phase sintering and then joints with cast iron by the heat of pouring. Compared with carburization, nitriding, plating, PVD and CVD which are conventional methods of improvement of the surface, this method has prominent features below described.

- 1) It is possible to make an improvement layer on the surface by utilizing the heat of pouring at the same time as casting.
- 2) It is possible to prepare the functional layer which has high resistance to such as abrasion, corrosion and heat by selecting suitable powders.
- 3) This method has a few steps and is cheap and easy.

Hard coated layer formed by diffusion-cementation with Fe-Cr powder [1] and fusion of low melting point alloying powders[2] have been reported as similar method. It is very difficult to develop layers with variously high performance on iron castings for their limited compositions.

We observed microstructure of coated layer and examine optimum conditions to form well coated layer such as combination and mass ratio of high performance powders and low melting point powders, and the thickness of coated powder and pouring temperature, etc. The hardness, resistance to wet abrasion and corrosion resistance of the coated iron castings were evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

We examined at first forming of hard and thick coated layer on iron castings of thick section (50mm in thickness) possessing resistance to wet abrasion corrosion [3,4] and secondary Ni or Cr rich coated layer on iron castings of thin section (10mm in thickness) possessing corrosion resistance [5].

The cast irons used by casting were FC(typical compositions: Fe-3.90C-2.10Si-0.33Mn-0.080P-0.012S) in thick section castings and FCD(typical compositions: Fe-3.60C-2.50Si-0.33Mn-0.005P-0.002S-0.045Mg) in thin section castings.

Composition, particle size and melting point of powders are show in Table1,2. Powders can be classified into two groups of the principle powders having high performance and powders having low melting point. Fe-Cr powder containing carbides (M_7C_3 and a little of $M_{23}C_6$) has high hardness [6]. Powders in SUS series (SUS304L,SUS430L) have function of corrosion resistance. FP7B powder is self-fused Ni based alloy with mean hardness of 720HV1 contained very hard phases of boride and carbide, has been used as self-melted and spraying powder [7]. Ni-P and Ni-Cr-P powders are alloying powders of eutectic component having low melting point.

Table1: Chemical composition of high performance powders

Powder	Chemical composition mass%								Particle Size •m	Melting Point K
	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Ni	Cr	Fe		
Fe-Cr	7.5	0.3	-	-	-	-	62.8	29.4	-74	1573
Ni	-	-	-	-	-	99.7	-	-	-45	1728
SUS304L	0.016	0.88	0.19	0.022	0.003	11.50	18.79	Bal.	-45	1671
SUS430L	0.013	0.88	0.19	0.013	0.009	0.12	16.11	Bal.	-45	1753

Table2: Chemical composition of low melting point powders

Powder	Chemical composition mass%							Particle Size •m	Melting Point K
	C	Si	P	Ni	Cr	Fe	B		
FP7B	0.8	4.7	-	69.9	17.0	4.1	3.5	-45	1333
Ni-P	-	-	11.4	88.6	-	-	-	-45	1198
Ni-Cr-P	-	-	10.6	76.8	12.6	-	-	-45	1198

PVAc(polyvinyl acetate) as binder generating little gas at pouring was used to fix mixed powders on the mold, as a consequence of testing various inorganic and organic materials.

Shapes and size of CO₂ molds are shown in Fig.1 (thick section) and Fig.2 (thin section). In Fig.1, Al₂O₃ powders were pasted in the thickness of 2mm on the mold for maintenance of pouring temperature before mixed powders were coated. Pouring temperature is 1623K and 1723K.

The specimens after pouring were cut off to observe their microstructures at the position of ••• (an odd number is from the ceiling and an even number is from the floor) in Fig.1 and at the position of ••• in Fig.2 to compare the influence of heat input from pouring on the formation of layer.

Fig.1: Shape of mold and specimen at each position

Fig.2: Shape of mold and specimen at each position

FORMATION OF HARD AND THICK COATING LAYER POSSESSING RESISTANCE TO ABRATION IN THICK CASTINGS

The Fe-Cr powder as principle powder which has good resistance to wet abrasion and FP7B, Ni-P and Ni-Cr-P powders as low melting point powders were selected.

The Fe-Cr powders alone were hardly sintered and then not consolidated as layer because of their high melting point at 1723K of pouring temperature. Three kinds powders of low melting point completely melted and dissolved into cast iron and were not formed coated layer at 1623K of pouring temperature. Mixed Fe-Cr and FP7B, Ni-P, Ni-Cr-P powders were examined with mass ratio from 90/10 to 10/90. The most closely coated layer was obtained about mass ratio of 65/35 or 50/50 and subsequent researches were then done in these ratio.

The microstructures of coated layers are shown in Fig.3 at the pouring temperatures of 1623K.

The liquid of FP7B had nicely wettability with Fe-Cr powder and their mixed powders formed fine coated layer in thickness of 1mm which had little pores.

The coated layer was strongly jointed with the parent material across carbide layer formed by diffusion of a part of powder layer.

The liquids of Ni-P and Ni-Cr-P were poorly wettable with Fe-Cr powder even at pouring temperature of 1723K, so coated layer with a lot of large pores were prepared.

In order to gain well coated layer at every location even if in Fe-Cr/FP7B, the mass ratio should be changed according to heat input. That is to say, it is necessary much quantity of FP7B(low melting point) as cooling rate was faster. The well coated layer was obtained at the ratio of 50/50 at the place of • or •.

In thick and large iron casting, coated layer was obtained easily and but should be kept in mind over-solution of powder because of enough quantity of heat. The microstructure of coated layer with Fe-Cr/FP7B=80/20 component is shown at center of floor in the mold size of 150×150×100(in thickness)mm in Fig 4.

Fig.3: Microstructure of coated layer

Pouring temperature 1623K

(a)Fe-Cr/FP7B=65/35, (b)Fe-Cr/Ni-P=65/35

(c)Fe-Cr/Ni-Cr-P=65/35

Fig.4: Microstructure of coated layer(1723K. Fe-Cr/FP7B=80/20)

According to the result of measurement of heating and then cooling temperature at position of coated layer after pouring, there was very difference of maximum temperature and cooling rate at each position(•••).We could obtain coated

layer with no scale off of powder layer on the ceiling as well as on the floor.

Hardness of coated layer is showed in Fig.5. The most hard coating layer was as hard as 800•900HV1 in surface area and 1000•1100HV1 (M_6C phase) in the interface of parent material in Fe-Cr/FP7B.

The results of wet abrasion test are shown in Fig.6. The coated cast iron showed 1/6 of FCD and 1/5 of wear resisting steel in weight loss in resistance to wet abrasion test of 3%NaCl solution for a month.

Compared with pearlite or ferrite cast iron which was etched with red rust, the coated cast iron was very little in weight loss and about 1/2 of 5%Ni cast iron in the immersion test in 3%NaCl solution.

Fig.6: Wet abrasion test

FORMATION OF COATED LAYER POSSESSING CORROSION RESISTANCE IN THIN CASTINGS

Ni, SUS304L and SUS430L powders having good corrosion and Ni-P and Ni-Cr-P powders having low melting point temperature were selected.

It was found that the combination of Ni/Ni-P formed the best layer because Ni-P powder including no Cr has lower melting point than Ni-Cr-P powder and the liquid also has the best wettability with Ni powder.

The change of microstructures depends on the quantity of coated powder are shown in Fig.7. The most thickness of layer was formed in thickness of 500•m in thickness at 180mg/cm². In 70mg/cm², the layer had little thickness because of powder layer to solute into cast iron. There was a part of flaking for coated layer from cast iron because of lack of heat in too thick powder layer like 360mg/cm².

The hardness of coated layer on iron cast is shown in Fig.8. The coated layer was as hard as

Fig.7: Microstructure of coated layer

- (a) 70mg/cm² (b) 130mg/cm²
- (c) 180mg/cm² (d) 360mg/cm²

Fig.5: Hardness of coated layer

100•200HV1 in the surface and about 400HV1 in the interface of parent material.

We recognized the area being as hard as about 400HV1 as martensitic phase which contained about 5% Ni with composition of Nihard cast iron [8,9]. According to analysis of EPMA, there was about 20%Ni near the surface and about 5%Ni in the depth of approximately 0.5mm from the surface. Martensitic phase was inclined to form in the surface of coated layer in case of thin powder layer as 70mg/cm².

Salt-spray corrosion test in 5%NaCl solution at 308K about 0.10MPa ,was done for samples as cast and after annealing scale removed by shot blasting. Coated iron castings was about 1/8 of FCD in weight loss in corrosion test after about 80 days.

The iron casting closely coated layer generated no red rust and but iron castings with porous layer generated etch pit with red rust and therefore proceeded the corrosion.

Finally, the coated layer with Ni/Ni-P on cast iron is shown schematically in Fig.9.

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Fig.8: Hardness of coated layer

Salt-spray corrosion test in 5%NaCl solution at 308K about 0.10MPa ,was done for samples as cast and after annealing scale removed by shot blasting. Coated iron castings was about 1/8 of FCD in weight loss in corrosion test after about 80 days.

Fig.9: Schema of coated layer (Ni/Ni-P)

CONCLUSION

The coating on iron castings was prepared by using a mixture of high performance powders and Ni-based alloy powders having low melting point as the coated powder on the mold. By the heat of pouring, their powders layers are consolidated during liquid-phase sintering and then jointed with cast iron .

In thickness section(50mm in thickness), the coated layer obtained for Fe-Cr/FP7B=65/35 was 1•2mm in thickness and hardness of 800•1100HV1 and had good resistance to wet abrasion and corrosion. In thin section(10mm in thickness), the layer obtained for Ni/Ni-P=50/50 was 300•500•m in thickness and had soft surface layer (100•200HV1) containing 10•20%Ni and therefore good corrosion resistance to spraying of 5%NaCl solution.

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